

Report about feasibility bioconversion of OFMSW into high- value products by bioelectrochemical systems

Deliverable 6.3

Lead Partner: AQUALIA
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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The bioelectrochemical system (BES) target is to bioelectrochemically convert the CO₂ contained in the biogas produced from the digestion of USS sludge or OFMSW into valuable organic compounds (mainly acetate). This prototype has been installed in DS 1 (Spain) treating biogas from OFMSW and will be further tested in DS 6 (Czech Republic) in future stages of the project, treating biogas from USS.

Deliverable 6.3 aims to describe and discuss the results obtained during 300 days of operation of the BES reactor in DS 1 (Spain). During batch mode operation, a maximum of 965 mg acetate d⁻¹ was achieved, while 545 mg acetate d⁻¹ was the highest production rate achieved during continuous operation.

Once stable continuous operation is achieved and optimum operation parameters identified, next steps include a closer look on the hydrogen production and the gas-phase composition. This will allow performing an energetic balance and techno-economic analyses.

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